

On Generalization Property of I^s -Open Sets in Ideal Topological Semigroups

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Abstract:- In this paper, we introduce and investigate a new class of I^s -open sets, called generalized I^s -open sets in ideal topological semigroups a space. We study some properties on this class, such as product and relativity. Further more, the relationships between this class and other known classes are introduced and studied.

Keywords:- Open Set; Ideal Topological Space, Topological Semigroup. *AMS Classification: Primary 54A05, 16W30.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The notion of an ideal topological spaces is introduced by Kuratowski, [7]. Many researcher studied about the an ideal topological spaces. An ideal I on a topological space (X, τ) is a nonempty collection of subsets of X which satisfies the following conditions:

1- if $A \in I$ and $B \subseteq A$ then $B \in I$, 2- if $A \in I$ and $B \in I$ then $A \cup B \in I$.

Applications to various fields were further investigated by Jankovic and Hamlett [2], Dontchev [6], and Arenas and et al. [4]. An ideal topological space is a topological space (X, τ) with an ideal I on X and it is denoted by (X, τ, I) .

This paper is organized as follows: Section 3 introduces the concept of generalized I^s -open sets in ideal topological semigroups with its relationship among other known sets. Section 4 introduces the properties of product and relativity of generalized I^s -open sets.

II. PRELIMINARIES

➤ *Theorem 2.1.*

[5] For a topological space (X, τ) and $A, B \subseteq X$, if B is an open set in X , then $Cl(A) \cap B \subseteq Cl(A \cap B)$.

➤ *Theorem 2.2.*

[5] For a topological space (X, τ) ,

- $Cl(X - A) = X - Int(A)$ for all $A \subseteq X$;
- $Int(X - A) = X - Cl(A)$ for all $A \subseteq X$.

➤ *Definition 2.3.*

[8] A subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is called a *generalized closed* (simply *g-closed*) *set*, if $Cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is an open subset of (X, τ) . The complement of *g-closed* set is called a *generalized open* (simply *g-open*) *set*.

➤ *Theorem 2.4.*

[8] Every closed set is a *g-closed* set.

➤ *Definition 2.5.*

A topological space (X, τ) is called:

- a $T_{1/2}$ -space [8] if every *g-closed* set is a closed set.
- a T_1 -space [5] if for each disjoint point $x \neq y \in X$, there are two open sets G and H in X such that $x \in H$, $y \in G$, $x \notin G$ and $y \notin H$.

➤ *Theorem 2.6.*

[8] A topological space (X, τ) is a $T_{1/2}$ -space if and only if every singleton set is either open or a closed set.

➤ *Theorem 2.7.*

[5] A topological space (X, τ) is a T_1 -space if and only if every singleton set is a closed set.

In an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) , $A^*(I)$ is

de- (X, τ, I) the ideal topological semigroup with

opined by: reation $\pi : X \times X \rightarrow X$,

where $\pi(x, y) = x$ or

$\pi(x, y) = y$ for all $x, y \in X$. $A^*(I) = \{x \in X : U \cap A \notin I \text{ for each open neighborhood } U \text{ of } x\}$

Is called the local function of A with respect to I and τ , [7]. When there is no chance for confusion $A^*(I)$ is denoted by A^* . For every ideal topological space (X, τ, I) , there exists a topology τ^* finer than τ , generated by the base

$$\beta(I, \tau) = \{U - I : U \in \tau \text{ and } I \in I\}.$$

Observe additionally that $Cl^*(A) = A \cup A^*$, [9] defines a Kuratowski closure operator for τ^* . $Int^*(A)$ will denote the interior of A in (X, τ^*) . If I is an ideal on topological space (X, τ) , then (X, τ, I) is called an ideal topological space.

➤ *Theorem 2.8.*

[3] Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space. Then for $A, B \subseteq X$, the following properties hold:

- $A \subseteq B$ implies that $A^* \subseteq B^*$;
- $G \in \tau$ implies that $G \cap A^* \subseteq (G \cap A)^*$;
- $A^* = Cl(A^*) \subseteq Cl(A)$;
- $(A \cup B)^* = A^* \cup B^*$;
- $(A^*)^* \subseteq A^*$.

By topological semigroup (X, τ) , we mean a topological space (X, τ) which is space with associated multiplication $* : X \times X \rightarrow X$ such that $*$ is continuous function from the product space $X \times X$ into X . By an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) , we mean an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) with associated multiplication $* : X \times X \rightarrow X$ such that $*$ is continuous function from the product space $X \times X$ into X . A pair (Y, \circ) is called *I-subspace* of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) if Y is a subspace of X and the continuous function \circ takes the product $Y \times Y$ into Y and $\circ(x, y) = *(x, y)$ for all $x, y \in Y$. We denote the operation of any *I-subspace* with the same symbol used for the operation on the an ideal topological semigroup under consideration. For any ideal topological space (X, τ, I) , we mean by

➤ *Definition 2.9.*

[1] A subset A of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) is said to be an I^s -open set if $A \subseteq Cl[Int^*(Cl^*(A))]$. The complement of I^s -open set is said to be an I^s -closed set. For an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) , the set of all I^s -closed sets in X denoted by $I^sC(X, \tau)$ and the set of all I^s -open sets in X denoted by $I^sO(X, \tau)$.

➤ *Theorem 2.10.*

[1] For a subset $A \subseteq X$ of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) , ${}_{1s}Cl(A) = A$ if and only if A is an I^s -closed set.

➤ *Theorem 2.11.*

[1] For a subset $A \subseteq X$ of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) , ${}_{1s}Int(A) = A$ if and only if A is an I^s -open set.

➤ *Theorem 2.12.*

[1] For a subsets $A, B \subseteq X$ of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) , the following hold:

- If $A \subseteq B$ then ${}_{1s}Cl(A) \subseteq {}_{1s}Cl(B)$;
- ${}_{1s}Cl(A) \cup {}_{1s}Cl(B) \subseteq {}_{1s}Cl(A \cup B)$;
- ${}_{1s}Cl(A \cap B) \subseteq {}_{1s}Cl(A) \cap {}_{1s}Cl(B)$;
- ${}_{1s}Cl(A) \subseteq Cl(A)$.

➤ *Theorem 2.13.*

[1] For a subsets $A, B \subseteq X$ of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) , the following hold:

- If $A \subseteq B$ then ${}_{1s}Int(A) \subseteq {}_{1s}Int(B)$;
- ${}_{1s}Int(A) \cup {}_{1s}Int(B) \subseteq {}_{1s}Int(A \cup B)$;
- ${}_{1s}Int(A \cap B) = {}_{1s}Int(A) \cap {}_{1s}Int(B)$;
- $Int(A) \subseteq {}_{1s}Int(A)$.

➤ *Theorem 2.14.*

[1] For a subset $A \subseteq X$ of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) , the following hold:

- ${}_{1s}Int(X - A) = (X - {}_{1s}Cl(A))$;
- ${}_{1s}Cl(X - A) = (X - I^sInt(A))$.

III. GENERALIZED I^s -OPEN SETS

➤ *Definition 3.1.*

A subset A of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) is called a generalized I^s -closed set (simply I^s_g -closed) if ${}_{1s}Cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open subset of (X, τ, I) . The complement of I^s_g -closed set is called a generalized I^s -open set (simply I^s_g -open).

For an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) , the set of all I^s_g -closed sets in X denoted by $I^s_gC(X, \tau)$ and the set of all I^s_g -open sets in X denoted by $I^s_gO(X, \tau)$.

➤ *Example 3.2.*

In an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) , where $X = \{a, b, c\}$,

$$\tau = \{\emptyset, X\}, I = \{\emptyset, \{a\}\}, \text{ and } \tau^* = \{\emptyset, X, \{b, c\}\}$$

$$I^s_gC(X, \tau) = P(X),$$

And

$$I^s_gO(X, \tau) = P(X).$$

➤ *Theorem 3.3.*

Every I^s -open set is an I^s_g -open set.

Proof. Let A be an I^s -open subset of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) . Then $X - A$ is I^s -closed set. Hence $X - A = {}_{1s}Cl(X - A) \subseteq U$ whenever $X - A \subseteq U$ and U is open set. That is, A is I^s_g -open set. \square

The converse of Theorem (3.3), no need to be true. In example (3.2), $\{a\}$ is I^s_g -open set but it is not I^s -open set.

➤ *Corollary 3.4.*

Every I^s -closed set is an I^s_g -closed set.

➤ *Theorem 3.5.*

Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological semigroup. If (X, τ) is a $T_{1/2}$ -space. Then every I^s_g -closed set in X is I^s -closed.

Proof. Let A be an I^s_g -closed set in (X, τ, I) . Suppose that A is not I^s -closed set. Then there is at least $x \in {}_{1s}Cl(A)$ such that $x \notin A$. Since (X, τ) is a $T_{1/2}$ space then by Theorem (2.6), $\{x\}$ is an open or closed set in X . If $\{x\}$ is a closed set in X then $X - \{x\}$ is an open set. Since $x \notin A$, we have $A \subseteq X - \{x\}$.

Since A is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set and $X - \{x\}$ is an open subset of X containing A , we get ${}_{1s}CI(A) \subseteq X - \{x\}$. Hence $x \in X - {}_{1s}CI(A)$ and this contradiction, because $x \in {}_{1s}CI(A)$. If $\{x\}$ is an open set then it is \mathcal{I}^s -open set. Since $x \in {}_{1s}CI(A)$ we have $\{x\} \cap A \neq \emptyset$. That is, $x \in A$ and this contradiction. Hence A is \mathcal{I}^s -closed set in (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) . \square

➤ **Theorem 3.6.**

Let (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) be an ideal topological semigroup. Every g -open set in (X, τ) is \mathcal{I}_g^s -open set.

Proof. Let A be a g -open set in (X, τ) . Then $X - A$ is g -closed set. Hence $X - A = Cl(X - A) \subseteq U$ whenever $X - A \subset U$ and U is open set. Since ${}_{1s}CI(X - A) \subseteq Cl(X - A)$, we get ${}_{1s}CI(X - A) \subseteq U$ whenever

$X - A \subseteq U$ and U is open set. Therefore $X - A$ is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set. That is A is \mathcal{I}_g^s -open set. \square

The converse of Theorem (3.6,) no need to be true. for Example,

➤ **Example 3.7.**

In a ideal topological semigroup

(X, τ, \mathcal{I}) , where $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, X, \{a, b\}\}$, $\mathcal{I} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}\}$ and $\tau^* = \{\emptyset, X, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}\}$,

$\{b, c\}$ is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -open set and it is not g -open set, because $U = \{a, b\}$ is an open set in (X, τ) and $\{a\} \subseteq U$ but $Cl(\{a\}) = X \neq U$.

➤ **Theorem 3.8.**

If A is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set in an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) and B is a closed set in (X, τ) then $A \cap B$ is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set.

Proof. Let U be an open subset of (X, τ) such that $A \cap B \subseteq U$. Since B is closed set in (X, τ) we obtain $U \cup (X - B)$ is an open set in (X, τ) . Since A is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set in X and $A \subseteq U \cup (X - B)$ so on ${}_{1s}CI(A) \subseteq U \cup (X - B)$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} {}_{1s}CI(A \cap B) &\subseteq {}_{1s}CI(A) \cap {}_{1s}CI(B) \subseteq {}_{1s}CI(A) \cap Cl(B) \\ &= {}_{1s}CI(A) \cap B \subseteq [U \cup (X - B)] \cap B \\ &\subseteq U \cap B \subseteq U. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $A \cap B$ is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set. \square

➤ **Theorem 3.9.**

For any $x \in X$ in an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) , either the set $\{x\}$ is \mathcal{I}^s -closed or the set $X - \{x\}$ is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed in (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) .

Proof. If $\{x\}$ is not \mathcal{I}^s -closed set in (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) then $\{x\}$ is not closed set in X and so $X - \{x\}$ is not open set in X . Then the set X is only open set in itself containing $\{x\}$ and hence ${}_{1s}CI(X - \{x\}) \subseteq X$. That is, $X - \{x\}$ is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed in (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) . \square

➤ **Theorem 3.10.**

A subset A of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed if and only if for each $x \in {}_{1s}CI(A)$, $Cl(\{x\}) \cap A \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. Suppose that A is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set in (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) and $x \in {}_{1s}CI(A)$ be any point. Let $Cl(\{x\}) \cap A = \emptyset$. Since $Cl(\{x\})$ is a closed set in X we obtain $X - Cl(\{x\})$ is an open set in X . Since $A \subseteq X - Cl(\{x\})$ and A is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set we get ${}_{1s}CI(A) \subseteq X - Cl(\{x\})$ but this contradicts with $x \in X - Cl(\{x\})$. Hence $Cl(\{x\}) \cap A \neq \emptyset$.

Conversely, suppose that for each $x \in {}_{1s}CI(A)$, $Cl(\{x\}) \cap A \neq \emptyset$ and U be any open set in X such that $A \subseteq U$. Let $x \in {}_{1s}CI(A)$. Then $Cl(\{x\}) \cap A \neq \emptyset$. Then there is at least $z \in Cl(\{x\})$ and $z \in A$. Then $z \in Cl(\{x\})$ and $z \in U$. Since U is an open set in X we get $\{x\} \cap U \neq \emptyset$. Hence $x \in U$ and so ${}_{1s}CI(A) \subseteq U$. Hence, A is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set. \square

➤ **Theorem 3.11.**

A subset A of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -open set if and only if $F \subseteq {}_{1s}Int(A)$ whenever $F \subseteq A$ and F is closed subset of (X, τ) .

Proof. Let A be an \mathcal{I}_g^s -open subset of X and F be a closed subset of (X, τ) such that $F \subseteq A$. Then

$X - A$ is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set, $X - A \subseteq X - F$ and $X - F$ is an open subset of (X, τ) . By Theorem(2.14), we get $X - {}_{1s}Int(A) = {}_{1s}CI(X - A) \subseteq X - F$, that is, $F \subseteq {}_{1s}Int(A)$.

Conversely, suppose that $F \subseteq {}_{1s}Int(A)$ where F is a closed subset of (X, τ) such that $F \subseteq A$. Then for any open subset U of (X, τ) such that $X - A \subseteq U$, we have $X - U \subseteq A$ and $X - U \subseteq {}_{1s}Int(A)$. Then by Theorem(2.14), $X - {}_{1s}Int(A) = {}_{1s}CI(X - A) \subseteq U$.

Hence $X - A$ is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed. That is, A is \mathcal{I}_g^s -open set. \square

➤ **Theorem 3.12.**

If A is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed subset of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, \mathcal{I}) then ${}_{1s}CI(A) - A$ contains no nonempty closed set in (X, τ) .

Proof. Suppose that ${}_{1s}CI(A) - A$ contains a nonempty closed set F in (X, τ) . Then

$$F \subseteq {}_{1s}CI(A) - A \subseteq {}_{1s}CI(A).$$

Since $A \subseteq {}_{1s}CI(A)$ we have $F \subseteq X - A$ and so $A \subseteq X - F$ is a closed set and $X - F$ is an open subset of (X, τ) , we conclude ${}_{1s}CI(A) \subseteq X - F$ and so $F \subseteq X - {}_{1s}CI(A)$. Therefore

$$F \subseteq {}_{1s}CI(A) \cap (X - {}_{1s}CI(A)) = \emptyset$$

$$X - F. \text{ Since } A \text{ is } \mathcal{I}_g^s$$

And so $F = \emptyset$. Hence ${}_{1s}CI(A) - A$ contains no nonempty closed set in (X, τ) . \square

➤ *Corollary 3.13.*

If A is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed subset of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) then ${}_{1s}Cl(A) - A$ is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -open set.

Proof. By Theorem (3.12), ${}_{1s}Cl(A) - A$ contains no nonempty closed set in (X, τ) and it is clear that $\emptyset \subseteq {}_{1s}Int({}_{1s}Cl(A) - A)$ then by Theorem (3.11), ${}_{1s}Cl(A) - A$ is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -open set in (X, τ, I) . \square

➤ *Theorem 3.14.*

If A is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed subset of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) and $B \subseteq X$. If

$$A \subseteq B \subseteq {}_{1s}Cl(A) \text{ we obtain } B \text{ is an } \mathcal{I}_g^s\text{-closed set.}$$

Proof. Let U be an open set in (X, τ) such that $B \subseteq U$. Then $A \subseteq B \subseteq U$. Since A is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set then ${}_{1s}Cl(A) \subseteq U$. Since $B \subseteq {}_{1s}Cl(A)$ then

$${}_{1s}Cl(B) \subseteq {}_{1s}Cl[{}_{1s}Cl(A)] = {}_{1s}Cl(A) \subseteq U.$$

That is, B is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set in (X, τ, I) . \square

➤ *Theorem 3.15.*

Let A be an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed subset of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) . Then $A = {}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A))$ if and only if ${}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A$ is a closed set in (X, τ) .

Proof. Let ${}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A$ be closed set in (X, τ) . Since ${}_{1s}Int(A) \subseteq A$ and $A \subseteq {}_{1s}Cl(A)$, we conclude ${}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) \subseteq {}_{1s}Cl(A)$. Then ${}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A \subseteq {}_{1s}Cl(A) - A$, this implies ${}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A \subseteq X - A \Rightarrow A \subseteq X - ({}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A)$.

Since A is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set and $X - ({}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A)$ is an open set in (X, τ) containing A , we have ${}_{1s}Cl(A) \subseteq X - ({}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A)$, this implies

$${}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A \subseteq X - {}_{1s}Cl(A).$$

Therefore,

$${}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A \subseteq {}_{1s}Cl(A) \cap (X - {}_{1s}Cl(A)) = \emptyset.$$

Hence ${}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A = \emptyset$, that is, ${}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) = A$.

Conversely, if $A = {}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A))$ then ${}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A = \emptyset$ and hence ${}_{1s}Cl({}_{1s}Int(A)) - A$ is a closed set in (X, τ) . \square

IV. PRODUCT AND RELATIVELY

For a bitopological semigroup (X, τ, ρ) and a subset A of X , the $\tau\rho$ -closure set of A is defined as the intersection of all $\tau\rho$ -closed sets containing A and it is denoted by ${}_{\tau\rho}Cl(A)$. The $\tau\rho$ -interior set of A is defined as the union of all $\tau\rho$ -open sets of X contained in A and it is denoted by ${}_{\tau\rho}Int(A)$.

➤ *Definition 4.1.*

A subset $A \subseteq X$ is said to be $I_{\tau\rho}$ -closed set in a bitopological semigroup (X, τ, ρ) if ${}_{\tau\rho}Cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open subset in (X, τ) . The complement of $I_{\tau\rho}$ -closed set is said to be $I_{\tau\rho}$ -open set.

➤ *Lemma 4.2.*

For a subset of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) ,

- ${}_{\tau\tau}Cl(A) = {}_{1s}Cl(A)$.
- ${}_{\tau\tau}Int(A) = {}_{1s}Int(A)$.

Proof. It is clear from the definitions.

➤ *Theorem 4.3.*

A subset $A \subseteq X$ is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set in an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) if and only if it is $I_{\tau\tau}$ -closed set in bitopological semigroup (X, τ, τ) .

Proof. It is clear from the definitions and Lemma (4.2).

➤ *Theorem 4.4.*

Let Y be an open subspace of an ideal topological semigroup (X, τ, I) and $A \subseteq Y$. If

A is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set in (X, τ, I) then A is $I_{\tau|Y, \tau|Y}$ -closed set in bitopological semigroup $(Y, \tau|Y, \tau|Y)$.

Proof. Let O be an open subset in $(Y, \tau|Y)$ such that $A \subseteq O$. Then $O = U \cap Y$ for some open set U in (X, τ) and so $A \subseteq U$. Since A is an \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set in (X, τ, I) , we get ${}_{1s}Cl(A) \subseteq U$. By Theorem (4.3) and Lemma (4.2), ${}_{\tau\tau}Cl|_Y(A) = {}_{1s}Cl(A)|_Y(A) = {}_{1s}Cl(A) \cap Y \subseteq U \cap Y = O$.

Hence A is $I_{\tau|Y, \tau|Y}$ -closed set in $(Y, \tau|Y, \tau|Y)$. \square

➤ *Theorem 4.5.*

Let Y be an open subspace of an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) and $A \subseteq Y$. If A is $I_{\tau|Y, \tau|Y}$ -closed set in bitopological semigroup $(Y, \tau|Y, \tau|Y)$ and Y is I^s -closed set in (X, τ, I) then A is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set in (X, τ, I) .

Proof. Let U be an open subset in (X, τ) such that $A \subseteq U$. Then $A \subseteq U \cap Y$ and $U \cap Y$ is open set in $(Y, \tau|Y)$. Since A is a $I_{\tau|Y, \tau|Y}$ -closed set in bitopological semigroup $(Y, \tau|Y, \tau|Y)$, we get ${}_{\tau\tau}Cl|_Y(A) \subseteq U \cap Y$. Since Y is an open set in (X, τ) and Y is an I^s -closed set in (X, τ, I) we have By Theorem (4.4) and Lemma (4.2),

$$\begin{aligned} {}_{1s}Cl(A) &= {}_{1s}Cl(A \cap Y) \subseteq {}_{1s}Cl(A) \cap {}_{1s}Cl(Y) \\ &= {}_{1s}Cl(A) \cap Y = {}_{1s}Cl|_Y(A) = {}_{\tau\tau}Cl|_Y(A) \\ &\subseteq U \cap Y \subseteq U. \end{aligned}$$

Hence A is \mathcal{I}_g^s -closed set in (X, τ, I) . \square

➤ *Lemma 4.6.*

Let (X, τ, I) and (Y, ρ, I^0) be two ideals topological semigroup. If $A \subseteq X$ and $B \subseteq Y$ then the following hold:

- $(\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0}) \text{Int}(A \times B) = {}_1\text{Int}(A) \times {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Int}(B)$.
- $(\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0}) \text{Cl}(A \times B) = {}_1\text{Cl}(A) \times {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Cl}(B)$.

Proof. 1. Let $(x, y) \in (\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0}) \text{Int}(A \times B)$. Then $(A \times B) \cap (U \times Y) \subseteq (A \times Y) \cap (U \times Y) = (A \cap U) \times Y = \emptyset \times Y = \emptyset$. by the definition there is at least one a $(\tau \times \rho)(\tau_1 \times \rho_1 \mathbf{0})$ -open set $U \times I$ in bitopological semigroup $(X_* \times Y, \tau \times \rho, \tau_1 \times \rho_1 \mathbf{0})$ such that $(x, y) \in U \times I \subseteq A \times B$. Then by Theorem (2.9) A is an \mathbf{I}^s -open set in (X_*, τ, \mathbf{I}) and B is a \mathbf{I}^s -open set in (Y, ρ, \mathbf{I}^0) . So $x \in U \subseteq A$ and $y \in I \subseteq B$. Then $x \in {}_1\text{Int}(A)$ and $y \in {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Int}(B)$. This implies $(x, y) \in {}_1\text{Int}(A) \times {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Int}(B)$. Therefore

$$(\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0}) \text{Int}(A \times B) \subseteq {}_1\text{Int}(A) \times {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Int}(B). \text{ Similar, } {}_1\text{Int}(A) \times {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Int}(B) \subseteq (\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0}) \text{Int}(A \times B).$$

2. Let $(x, y) \in {}_1\text{Cl}(A) \times {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Cl}(B)$. Then $x \in {}_1\text{Cl}(A)$ or $y \in {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Cl}(B)$. If $x \in {}_1\text{Cl}(A)$ then by Theorem (2.9) there is an \mathbf{I}^s -open set U in (X_*, τ, \mathbf{I}) containing x such that $A \cap U = \emptyset$. Then by Theorem (4.3) U is a $\tau \tau_1$ -open set in bitopological semigroup (X_*, τ, τ_1) containing x and Y is a $\rho \rho_1 \mathbf{0}$ -open set in bitopological semigroup $(Y, \rho, \rho_1 \mathbf{0})$ containing y . Hence $U \times Y$ is a $(\tau \tau_1)(\rho \rho_1 \mathbf{0})$ -open set in bitopological semigroup $(X_* \times Y, \tau \times \rho, \tau_1 \times \rho_1 \mathbf{0})$ containing (x, y) and Then by Lemma (4.6), ${}_1\text{Cl}(A) \times {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Cl}(B) = (\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0}) \text{Cl}(A \times B) \subseteq U_1 \times U_2$.

This implies, ${}_1\text{Cl}(A) \subseteq U_1$ and ${}_1\text{Cl}(B) \subseteq U_2$. Hence A is an \mathbf{I}_g^s -closed set in (X_*, τ, \mathbf{I}) and B is an \mathbf{I}_g^s -closed set in (Y, ρ, \mathbf{I}^0) .

Conversely, suppose that A is an \mathbf{I}_g^s -closed set in (X_*, τ, \mathbf{I}) and B is \mathbf{I}_g^s -closed set in (Y, ρ, \mathbf{I}^0) . Let $U_1 \times U_2$ be an open set in $(X \times Y, \tau \times \rho)$ and $U_1 \times U_2 \subseteq A \times B$. Then U_1 is an open set in (X, τ) and U_2 is an open set in (Y, ρ) such that $U_1 \subseteq A$ and $U_2 \subseteq B$. By the hypothesis, ${}_1\text{Cl}(A) \subseteq U_1$ and ${}_1\text{Cl}(B) \subseteq U_2$. Hence by Lemmas (4.6) and (4.2),

$$(\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0}) \text{Cl}(A \times B) = {}_1\text{Cl}(A) \times {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Cl}(B) \subseteq U_1 \times U_2.$$

Hence $A \times B$ is $I_{(\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0})}$ -closed set in bitopological semigroup $(X_* \times Y, \tau \times \rho, \tau_1 \times \rho_1 \mathbf{0})$. \square

This implies $(x, y) \in (\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0}) \text{Cl}(A \times B)$. Therefore

$$(\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0}) \text{Cl}(A \times B) \subseteq {}_1\text{Cl}(A) \times {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Cl}(B).$$

Similar,

$${}_1\text{Cl}(A) \times {}_1\mathbf{0}\text{Cl}(B) \subseteq (\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0}) \text{Cl}(A \times B).$$

➤ *Theorem 4.7.*

Let (X_*, τ, \mathbf{I}) and (Y, ρ, \mathbf{I}^0) be two ideals topological semigroups. A subset $A \times B \subseteq X \times Y$ is $I_{(\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0})}$ -closed set in bitopological semigroup $(X_* \times Y, \tau \times \rho, \tau_1 \times \rho_1 \mathbf{0})$ if and only if A is an \mathbf{I}_g^s -closed set in (X_*, τ, \mathbf{I}) and B is an \mathbf{I}_g^s -closed set in (Y, ρ, \mathbf{I}^0) .

Proof. Suppose that $A \times B$ is $I_{(\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0})}$ -closed set in bitopological semigroup $(X_* \times Y, \tau \times \rho, \tau_1 \times \rho_1 \mathbf{0})$. Let U_1 be an open set in (X, τ) and U_2 be an open set in (Y, ρ) such that $U_1 \subseteq$

A and $U_2 \subseteq B$. Then $U_1 \times U_2$ be an open set in $(X \times Y, \tau \times \rho)$ and $U_1 \times U_2 \subseteq A \times B$. Since $A \times B$ is $I_{(\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0})}$ -closed set in $(X_* \times Y, \tau \times \rho, \tau_1 \times \rho_1 \mathbf{0})$ we obtain $(\tau \times \rho)(\tau \times \rho \mathbf{I} \mathbf{0}) \text{Cl}(A \times B) \subseteq U_1 \times U_2$.

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